

Drug Repurposing in the Genomic Era: A Strategic Approach towards Precision Oncology

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ABSTRACT:

Drug repurposing offers a promising strategy to accelerate cancer treatment by finding new uses for existing drugs, reducing developmental time and cost while leveraging known safety profiles. This approach addresses key limitations in conventional oncology drug development, particularly the inefficiencies of single-target strategies and high failure rates in early phase trials. Repurposed drugs provide clinicians with additional therapeutic options, often suited for combination therapies and personalized regimens. However, substantial challenges persist, ranging from regulatory and financial disincentives to underpowered clinical studies and dosing uncertainties. Despite these barriers, advancements in omics technologies, real-world data analytics, and pharmacogenomics are paving the way for more precise and impactful repurposing efforts. With continued investment, innovative trial models, and multi-disciplinary collaboration, drug repurposing could become a foundational strategy in precision oncology, reshaping the future of cancer care.

Keywords: Drug Repurposing, Precision Oncology, Cancer, Clinical Trials, Metformin, Off-label Drugs.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Cancer remains one of the leading causes of death worldwide, despite the availability of various therapies such as chemotherapy, targeted therapy and immunotherapy. Although remarkable progress has been made in cancer research the global cancer burden continues to pose a significant challenge with an estimated 19.3 million new cases and 10 million deaths were reported in 2020¹. Existing cancer treatments face significant limitations such as drug resistance, severe side effects and high costs. In addition to this the process of developing new cancer therapies is both time-consuming and expensive, typically requiring 10 to 15 years to bring a drug from discovery to market. These difficulties pressurise us for alternative approaches that are more efficient, affordable and capable of meeting the unmet clinical demands in oncology². One of the best strategies to overcome such hurdles is drug repurposing also referred as drug repositioning. It has emerged to be a promising approach that identifies new therapeutic applications for existing drugs beyond their labelled indications. This is made possible by utilising established

pharmacokinetics, safety profiles, and manufacturing processes of approved and investigational drugs which will significantly reduce development timelines and costs³. On an average drug repurposing reduces development time of drug from 3-8 years and nearly 60% likelihood of success in clinical trials when compared to developing entirely new drugs. These advantages make drug repurposing particularly applicable in oncology where rapid translation of research into clinical practice is critical⁴.

Thalidomide originally developed as sedative but later withdrawn due to its teratogenicity but later was repurposed as a key therapy for multiple myeloma. Similarly, metformin a widely used anti diabetic drug has demonstrated anti-cancer effects in preclinical and clinical studies with ongoing trails investigating its role in cancer prevention and treatment⁵. Another example disulfiram a medication for alcohol dependence has shown anticancer activity in inhibiting proteasomes and inducing oxidative stress showing encouraging results in early phase clinical trials. These discoveries underline the transformative potential of repurposed drugs especially for cancers that are

resistant to conventional therapies⁶. Apart from the above benefits drug repurposing offers an opportunity to improve access to cancer care globally. Much of the drugs repurposed at present are off patent making them more affordable and accessible for low- and middle-income countries where access to expensive cancer therapies is limited⁷. Despite its potential, the clinical implementation of repurposed drugs faces significant obstacles. Regulatory complexities, intellectual property disputes and limited financial support often results in slow progress. In addition to these promising preclinical findings do not always translate into clinical success emphasizing the need for stronger translational framework³. Adaptive trails and basket trails are increasingly used to accelerate the evaluation of repurposed drugs and advances in technology strengthened drug repurposing field and is strategically executed by the help of computational methods like network pharmacology and screening of novel drug target interactions and validating repurposing hypothesis⁸. This approach is particularly necessary in oncology where the complexity of cancer biology often requires multi-targeted therapeutic approaches. This narrative review explores the promise of drug repurposing in oncology by examining key examples and discussing innovative strategies to accelerate clinical adoption and underscores the potential of repurposed therapies to provide affordable and effective cancer treatment worldwide.

2. Strategies and Methodologies for Identifying Repurposing Candidates in Cancer:

Identification of suitable candidates for drug repurposing in cancer involves a combination of experimental, computational and clinical strategies designed to identify new therapeutic indications for existing compounds.

2.1. Traditional and serendipitous discoveries:

Serendipity has always been an underrated driver of pharmaceutical innovation; with numerous therapies especially in cancer they emerged as accidental yet ground-breaking discoveries. In oncology 35.2% of anti-cancer drugs have been identified unexpectedly. Out of 88 anticancer drugs analysed, 13 were discovered directly through chance and 18 are chemical derivatives of those discoveries. Notable examples are cisplatin discovered by a researcher where he was observing platinum electrodes inhibited bacterial cell division and nitrogen mustards like mechlorethamine had shown effect whose effects on white blood cell counts during chemical warfare investigations led to its repurposing as a cancer treatment⁹. Thalidomide once withdrawn from market due to its severe birth defect risks was later reintroduced in oncology after its ability to inhibit angiogenesis and was used in treatment of multiple myeloma. Similarly, tamoxifen a popular drug used in management of hormone receptor positive breast

cancer was once developed as a potential contraceptive. These examples highlight the critical role of observational insights arising not only from controlled experiments but also from unanticipated clinical outcomes and real-world usage¹⁰. Traditional medicine systems particularly ayurveda and Korean traditional medicine have long contributed to evolution of cancer treatment by using empirical knowledge about healing practices and medicinal plants. Ayurveda, an ancient Indian system of medicine has been used for over 5000 years where cancer is a problem caused by imbalances in body's natural energies called as tridoshas along with weak tissue healing. It doesn't just focus on the disease but treats the whole person which includes herbal medicines, a healthy diet, yoga, meditation and changes in daily habits to bring the body back into balance and support healing. Plant derived compounds include curcumin that possess anti tumor activity and *Withania somnifera* targets oncogenic pathways like Notch-1, Akt/NF-kB exhibiting strong antiproliferative activity in colon cancer cell lines¹¹. (Murari Bhandari) Similarly Korean traditional medicine has shown similar potential where researchers employed modern screening and identified a compound called rutin, which is usually a flavonoid extracted from herbs like *Crataegus pinnatifida* is used as a potent anti-breast cancer agent and this works by inhibiting EGFR signalling and reduces tumor growth in preclinical models¹². Looking at traditional remedies through the lens of drug repurposing it gives us a fresh way to find new uses for old compounds, just like how modern drugs have sometimes surprised us with unreal benefits, age old herbal medicines could also hold hidden potential for treating cancer when combined with today's scientific tools.

2.2. Omics driven approaches:

Recent advances in omics technologies such as genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics are driving this shift by helping researchers understand the molecular mechanisms of cancer. In bladder cancer especially in high-risk non-muscle invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC), omics-based repurposing began with analysing gene and protein expression patterns from patient samples. Using tools like connectivity map (Cmap) researchers compared bladder cancer specific molecular profiles with those generated by various drugs to identify compounds that could reverse aggressive tumor phenotypes. One such compound called WYE-354 an mTOR pathway inhibitor was found to suppress proliferation and colony formation in bladder cancer cells validating computational prediction with functional outcomes¹³. For chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL), a large-scale study of all proteins in the cell called proteomics was performed. CLL's clinical course can vary greatly between patients and proteomic profiling has helped to reveal distinct

molecular subtypes and pathways driving disease progression. Researchers integrated proteomic, genomic and transcriptomic data to build a systems level view of disease. Using this, they identified differently expressed proteins, mapped them to essential signalling networks, and then matched these targets with repurposed drugs that are already in use for other drugs. Cytoskeletal modelling and metabolism have emerged as promising therapeutic entry points. The recommended workflow combined computational modelling with experimental validation ensuring that predictions could be translated into clinical applications¹⁴. This research is a significant step towards personalised medicine that was made possible due to combination of computational modelling along with data driven omics approach.

Similarly in case of triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) researchers took a comprehensive multi-omics approach, integrating transcriptomics, interactomics and metabolomics to identify new therapeutic strategies. By combining gene expression data from large breast cancer cohorts like TCGA and METABRIC, scientists applied a method called network entropy to spot clusters of highly active and dysregulated genes. This revealed three key driver modules like EDD, DHX9 and AURKA which were linked to cancer promoting pathways such as RAS, P13K, Rb/E2F and showed high expression of cell cycle proteins like CHK1 and cyclin B1 in aggressive tumours. By using L1000CDS2 tool with disease related gene patterns 80 repurposable compounds like selumetinib, oxymetholone, oxaprozin and so on are identified. Using personalised models from over 900 breast cancer patients the study identified basal like TNBC tumours heavily depended more on amino acid pathways¹⁵. These real-life examples are clear examples of how multi-omics integration is making drug repurposing more precise, efficient and aligned with more targeted ways to treat cancers.

2.3. Computational and in silico methods:

To explore existing drugs with potential anti-cancer effects, this study used computational techniques to identify dual inhibitors targeting key immune-related proteins. A total of 2315 FDA-approved drugs were virtually screened using the Drugrep webserver to identify candidates against HDAC6 and VISTA. Bexarotene was identified as the top HDAC6 inhibitor, while oxymorphone showed the highest affinity for VISTA. Molecular dynamics simulations over 100 ns confirmed the stable binding of both drugs to their targets. Bexarotene demonstrated a strong binding free energy of -51.7 kcal/mol compared to reference and oxymorphone/VISTA interaction yielded significant results and these results suggest that Bexarotene and Oxymorphone, though originally approved for other uses hold promise as a novel dual targeted therapy approach in cancer immunotherapy¹⁶. Analysing drug-target and disease-gene networks allows researchers to

uncover drugs that can act on multiple cancer-related pathways simultaneously. Instead of focusing on a single target, this approach maps how drugs interact across entire biological systems and identify key genes driving cancer progression. By overlaying these networks, it's possible to find compounds often repurposed drugs that can influence critical pathways. A clear example of this network-based approach is seen with *Hedyotis diffusa willd* (HDW) a traditional Chinese herb studied for colorectal cancer. Researchers found its active compound could target multiple high impact cancer genes, affecting key pathways like P13K-AKT, MAPK, and Wnt/beta catenin. HDW simultaneously suppress KRAS/BRAF driven MAPK signalling and restores APC mediated beta catenin degradation along with induction of G1 arrest via CDK2 down regulation deciphering its multi target therapy that aligns with systems level strategy of network pharmacology¹⁷. Network pharmacology refines precision oncology by mapping validated cancer driver genes into network models and repurposing existing drugs that act synergistically on these models and not just on single mutations. Detecting the patient specific modules that are disrupted then guides low toxicity drug combinations offering more targeted and more effective treatments.

2.4. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:

Traditional drug repurposing discoveries were made by chance often based on clinical observation and experimental luck, but Artificial intelligence has shifted this equation by enabling systematic, data driven approaches that are faster, more cost effective and less prone to failure compared to developing new drugs from scratch. Using advanced algorithms ranging from supervised learning models and deep neural networks to matrix factorisation, kernel-based methods, and natural language processing AI can predict how drugs will interact with cancer targets, even in presence of mutations by help of platforms like ChEMBL, Drug repurposing Hub and Drug target commons serve as foundational databases, while ML models analyse patterns across millions of compound-protein interactions to generate actionable predictions. Most importantly AI is not just about computational predictions when integrated with multi omic data from cancer cell lines and patient derived samples, it helps in identifying context specific therapeutic opportunities¹⁸. Axitinib drug originally approved as a VEGFR inhibitor for real cell carcinoma, axitinib was repurposed for chronic myeloid leukaemia (CML) and acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) after AI led investigations revealed its unexpected binding to BCR-ABL1 fusion protein particularly T3151 mutation variant, this discovery led to a clinical trial combining axitinib with bosutinib (NCT0278403). Similarly, the MT-DTI deep learning model predicted drugs targeting SARS-CoV-2 proteins, identifying atazanavir (HIV

protease inhibitor) as a potent candidate^{19,20}. This model's success tells us how similar approaches can discover antiviral and anticancer repurposing opportunities especially in virus associated cancers like HPV positive cervical or EBV related lymphomas.

Along with above discussed strategies high throughput phenotypic screening of cancer cell lines or organoids helps identify FDA approved drugs that induce anti-cancer effects without known targets. For instance, 22 active compounds were found against pancreatic cancer organoids. Clinical data mining of real-world evidence like Employee Health Records can reveal unexpected cancer benefits from non-cancer drugs such as metformin. All together these methods identify drug repurposing candidates in oncology.

3. Candidates in Cancer Drug Repurposing:

Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) vaccine (superficial bladder cancer), Thalidomide (multiple myeloma), and Propranolol (infantile haemangioma) are the only three specifically repurposed and approved drugs for cancer treatment. The Repurposing Drugs in Oncology (ReDO) projects database contains 268 drugs that are licensed for non-cancer indications but have published evidence of anticancer activity. These drugs are currently being investigated or used off-label. 164 (46%) of these 356 repurposed drugs are involved in clinical trials. About 94 drugs have at least some human data available regarding their use in repurposed cancer therapies, with 52 under clinical trials. At least 17 cancer medicines are commonly used off-label in various cancer types despite a lack of formal approval for these specific indications. A dedicated database for repurposing clinical trials (ReDO_Trials_DB) includes 805 trials involving the use of repurposed drugs for cancer. Metformin is the most frequently studied repurposed drug in these trials (128 trials)^{7,21–24}. These are summarised in Table 1.

3.1 Metformin:

Metformin, originally used for type 2 diabetes, has been identified as having potential anticancer properties. This potential was first suggested by epidemiological studies showing reduced cancer incidence in diabetic patients using metformin. This observation was researched for its mechanisms and applications in cancer therapy. Metformin exerts its anticancer effects through multiple molecular mechanisms. It activates AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), which is a cellular energy sensor triggered by an increased AMP/ATP ratio. After activation, AMPK inhibits the mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathway, resulting in reduced protein synthesis, cell growth, and proliferation in cancer cells^{25,26}. Metformin also suppresses key oncogenic signalling pathways, including receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) activity, PI3K/Akt pathway, and mTOR pathways, which are important regulators of cancer growth, metabolism, and survival²⁷. Metformin

selectively targets cancer stem cells (CSCs), impairing their regeneration capacity and reduces their role in tumour initiation, metastasis, drug resistance, and recurrence²⁷. Metformin modulates systemic metabolism by decreasing circulating levels of insulin and insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), thereby indirectly inhibiting insulin/IGF-1 receptor-mediated pathways that promote tumour progression²⁶. Clinical investigations have reported that metformin may improve tumour proliferation markers, notably by reducing Ki-67 expression in breast cancer patients who are not insulin-resistant²⁸. In endometrial cancer, the use of metformin as monotherapy has similarly been associated with a marked decrease in Ki-67, supporting its potential direct antiproliferative activity in this malignancy²⁸. Early clinical data also suggest that metformin may enhance overall survival and reduce recurrence rates in patients with gastric, renal, and oesophageal cancers²⁶. Laboratory studies further support these findings, demonstrating metformin's ability to influence key features of cancer biology, such as cellular proliferation and metabolism. Additionally, when used alongside conventional therapies, it appears to exert a synergistic effect in models of thyroid, prostate, and head and neck cancers²⁹. A number of clinical trials are currently underway to evaluate metformin's role in cancer treatment across various tumour types. These studies are designed to confirm its anticancer potential and to determine how best it can be used in combination with other therapies^{28,29}. Despite promising preclinical and early clinical results, several challenges remain. Notably, the ability to translate laboratory outcomes into consistent patient benefit is still uncertain, and its effectiveness across different cancer types as well as its impact on drug resistance—requires further study. Large-scale randomized controlled trials will be critical to establishing its clinical value and defining its place in oncology treatment protocols^{26,29}.

3.2 Aspirin:

Aspirin, widely recognized for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties, has also drawn substantial interest for its potential role in cancer prevention and therapy. While traditionally used to manage pain and cardiovascular conditions, growing evidence from preclinical and clinical research suggests that aspirin may exert antitumor effects through several biological pathways. These findings have prompted further investigation into its mechanisms and therapeutic relevance in oncology. The association between aspirin use and reduced cancer incidence was first noted in epidemiological studies, which reported a lower risk of developing certain malignancies among long-term users^{30,31}. Subsequent mechanistic studies revealed that aspirin modulates cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) activity and downregulates prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) synthesis—both of which are known to play critical roles in inflammation-driven tumorigenesis^{30,31}.

Aspirin's anticancer activity is attributed to its ability to induce apoptosis and suppress cell proliferation across various tumour models. These effects are primarily mediated through COX inhibition, but also extend to the regulation of non-coding RNAs involved in cancer signaling pathways^{32,33}. Additionally, aspirin influences key cellular processes such as angiogenesis and immune modulation, affecting multiple cell types within the tumour microenvironment³¹. Clinical and observational studies have shown aspirin's potential in reducing the risk and progression of colorectal, breast, and prostate cancers^{30,34}. Several clinical trials, both ongoing and completed, have reported improved survival outcomes and reduced metastasis when aspirin is used as an adjunct to conventional therapies^{33,34}. The clinical application of aspirin has concerns regarding adverse events, particularly gastrointestinal bleeding. Furthermore, ongoing research is needed to clarify its precise mechanisms in different cancer types and to establish safe and effective dosing strategies^{31,33}.

3.3 Propranolol:

Propranolol, a non-selective beta-adrenergic receptor antagonist long established in the treatment of cardiovascular conditions such as hypertension and arrhythmias, has gained attention in oncology for its potential anticancer effects. Its repurposing as an anticancer agent was first suggested through epidemiological studies that observed a lower incidence of certain cancers in patients who had been chronically treated with beta-blockers. This association prompted further investigation, and subsequent preclinical research demonstrated that propranolol could inhibit cancer cell proliferation, reduce invasive behaviour, and modulate immune responses across various tumour models³⁵. In colorectal cancer, propranolol has been shown to enhance antitumor immunity by improving T-cell responses and reducing systemic inflammation, thereby potentiating the effects of chemotherapeutic agents like irinotecan³⁶. In bladder cancer models, the drug inhibits the Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger 1 (NHE1), which disrupts intracellular pH regulation and induces apoptosis in malignant cells³⁷. In ovarian cancer, propranolol exerts its effects through activation of the reactive oxygen species (ROS)/JNK signalling pathway, leading to cell cycle arrest and programmed cell death³⁸. Several clinical trials are underway to evaluate propranolol in combination with established cancer therapies, particularly in colorectal and bladder cancers, with some completed studies already demonstrating favourable outcomes supporting its role as an adjunct treatment³⁷. Although findings to date are promising, further research is required to clarify the full spectrum of propranolol's mechanisms in tumour suppression and to determine optimal dosing and treatment protocols within oncology practice.

3.4 Carvedilol:

Carvedilol, a non-selective beta-adrenergic blocker originally developed for managing hypertension and heart failure, has recently been investigated for its anticancer potential. Its transition from cardiovascular therapy to oncology was prompted by findings from phosphoproteomic profiling, which revealed its capacity to interfere with epidermal growth factor (EGF)-induced signalling, specifically by inhibiting ERK nuclear translocation, a critical event in the progression of many cancers³⁹. Initial evidence of its chemopreventive potential came from preclinical studies demonstrating its ability to prevent skin carcinogenesis. Beyond its interaction with EGF signalling, carvedilol exhibits notable antioxidative effects, helping to reduce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and associated DNA damage, particularly in oestrogen receptor-negative breast cancer models. Further studies have shown that carvedilol can inhibit the PI3K/AKT and Src signaling pathways, both of which are central to cancer cell proliferation, migration, and invasion⁴⁰. Preclinical models have demonstrated its therapeutic promise in melanoma and breast cancer, with significant suppression of tumour growth observed in xenograft systems^{39,40}. Its multifaceted effects on signalling pathways suggest a valuable role in chemoprevention, especially in breast cancer. Clinical research into carvedilol's use in oncology is ongoing, with current trials focusing on its safety profile and efficacy when used in combination with established cancer therapies. While early findings are encouraging, further research is required to elucidate its mechanisms more fully and determine optimal clinical application. Broader exploration of such repurposed agents may continue to expand the therapeutic landscape in oncology.

3.5 Atorvastatin:

Atorvastatin, a commonly prescribed statin used in the management of hypercholesterolemia, has recently attracted interest for its potential application in cancer therapy. Although originally developed for cardiovascular indications, research over the past decade has identified antitumor effects associated with its use. The anticancer potential of atorvastatin was initially highlighted through computational analyses that revealed synthetic lethal interactions involving genes linked to cancer metastasis⁴¹. Mechanistically, atorvastatin exerts its effects by inhibiting the mevalonate pathway, a critical route for cholesterol biosynthesis and cell membrane integrity. This inhibition results in cell cycle arrest and induction of apoptosis in various cancer models. Furthermore, atorvastatin has been shown to downregulate markers of cancer stemness and disrupt key oncogenic signalling pathways, including β -catenin and STAT3^{42,43}. Preclinical studies have shown its efficacy in several cancer types. In gastric cancer, atorvastatin effectively targets cancer stem cells, reducing their proliferative capacity and suppressing tumour sphere

formation⁴². In ovarian cancer, it promotes programmed cell death and reduces tumours invasiveness, likely through modulation of angiogenic and fibrotic mediators such as VEGF and TGF- β 1 (Chen et al., 2024). Clinical trials, both ongoing and completed, continue to evaluate atorvastatin's role in oncology, with some reporting improved survival outcomes and lower recurrence rates when used adjunctively (Zaky et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). Nonetheless, variability in response across cancer types and patient populations underscores the need for further clinical investigation to define its optimal application in cancer therapy.

3.6 Thalidomide:

Thalidomide and its immunomodulatory derivatives, lenalidomide and pomalidomide, have become important therapeutic agents in oncology, despite their controversial beginnings. Thalidomide was initially introduced in the 1950s as a sedative and for the management of morning sickness in pregnant women. However, it was soon withdrawn from the market due to its severe teratogenic effects. Decades later, renewed interest in thalidomide arose after studies revealed its anti-inflammatory and anti-angiogenic properties, leading to its successful repurposing for the treatment of multiple myeloma and other haematological disorders. The drug was subsequently found to inhibit tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) while enhancing interleukin-2 (IL-2) production, thereby promoting T-cell activation and leading to cancer cell growth inhibition⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Thalidomide has since been approved for the treatment of multiple myeloma and certain myelodysplastic syndromes and is currently under evaluation in advanced clinical trials for these indications.

Lenalidomide:

Lenalidomide was developed as a structural analogue of thalidomide to improve efficacy and minimize adverse effects. Its mechanism of action involves binding to cereblon (CRBN), a component of the E3 ubiquitin ligase complex. This interaction promotes the degradation of key transcription factors that suppress T-cell activation, thus enhancing the immune system's ability to target malignant cells^{45,47}. Lenalidomide is now FDA-approved for the treatment of multiple myeloma and myelodysplastic syndromes, with numerous phase II and III trials ongoing to assess its role in other hematologic cancers⁴⁷.

Pomalidomide:

Pomalidomide, another next-generation derivative of thalidomide, was developed to further improve clinical outcomes in resistant or relapsed malignancies. Like lenalidomide, it enhances T-cell activity and suppresses TNF- α production, contributing to its antitumor effects^{44,46}. Pomalidomide is approved for use in multiple myeloma, particularly in patients who

have relapsed after previous lines of therapy, and its utility in other cancer types is currently being investigated through clinical trials (Teo, 2005). Although these agents have significantly advanced the treatment of hematologic cancers, concerns remain regarding their adverse effect profiles, particularly in long-term use. Continued research is focused on optimizing their efficacy while reducing toxicity, as well as developing newer analogues with improved pharmacologic profiles.

3.7 Chloroquine:

Chloroquine (CQ) and Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ), originally developed as antimalarial and antirheumatic agents, have gained considerable interest in oncology due to their capacity to inhibit autophagy a cellular process often exploited by cancer cells for survival under stress. Their repurposing for cancer treatment has been supported by preclinical and clinical findings demonstrating their ability to sensitize tumours to chemotherapy and radiation.

Chloroquine was first identified for its anticancer potential through studies showing its ability to block autophagy, specifically by preventing the fusion of autophagosomes with lysosomes. This disruption results in the accumulation of dysfunctional organelles and subsequent cancer cell death^{48,49}. Moreover, CQ has been shown to enhance the cytotoxic effects of chemotherapeutic agents such as topotecan by counteracting autophagy-mediated resistance⁵⁰. It has been tested in several cancer types, including glioblastoma, breast cancer, and non-small cell lung cancer. Clinical trials have evaluated its use as an adjuvant therapy, with some studies reporting improved therapeutic response when used in combination with standard treatments such as chemotherapy and radiation^{51,52}. However, results have been mixed, highlighting variability in clinical outcomes across tumour types and study designs⁴⁸.

Hydroxychloroquine:

Hydroxychloroquine, a less toxic derivative of chloroquine, shares similar autophagy-inhibitory properties and has been widely studied in preclinical cancer models. Like CQ, HCQ blocks autophagic flux, but it also appears to enhance the effects of targeted molecular therapies, offering a potential strategy to overcome drug resistance in various cancers^{48,49}. HCQ has been explored in malignancies such as glioblastoma, breast cancer, and pancreatic cancer. Clinical trials have primarily assessed its utility in combination regimens with chemotherapy or molecularly targeted agents. While some studies have demonstrated clinical benefit, results have varied depending on cancer type and therapeutic context^{48,49}. CQ and HCQ in experimental and early-phase clinical settings, inconsistencies in trial outcomes emphasize the need for further investigation. A deeper understanding of their pharmacodynamics, optimal

dosing, and interaction with other treatments is required to refine their role in oncology. The development of more selective autophagy inhibitors may also improve treatment outcomes and expand therapeutic options in the future ⁴⁸.

3.8 Disulfiram:

Disulfiram (DSF), initially developed for the management of chronic alcoholism, has recently attracted interest for its potential use in oncology. The drug's anticancer properties were first recognized through *in vitro* studies showing cytotoxic effects on various cancer cell lines. Subsequent research, supported by early-phase clinical trials, revealed that DSF operates through several mechanisms that are relevant to tumours suppression and therapeutic enhancement. A key mechanism involves the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative stress and the induction of apoptosis in malignant cells ⁵³. Additionally, DSF interferes with the ubiquitin-proteasome system, thereby inhibiting proteasomal degradation and disrupting protein homeostasis essential for tumours cell survival ⁵⁴. One of its most notable effects is its ability to target aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH), an enzyme highly expressed in cancer stem cells (CSCs), making DSF a candidate for reducing tumor relapse and resistance ⁵⁵. DSF also acts as a chemosensitizer, enhancing the efficacy of conventional chemotherapeutics by inhibiting drug efflux pumps such as P-glycoprotein and reversing resistance pathways ⁵⁶. Clinical investigations have focused on various tumor types. In breast cancer, studies have demonstrated improved survival outcomes when DSF is used in conjunction with copper, which amplifies its cytotoxic effect ⁵⁷. DSF has also shown potential in haematological malignancies, and ongoing clinical trials are evaluating its role in treatment-resistant blood cancers ⁵³. Moreover, its efficacy has been explored in solid tumours including prostate and pancreatic cancers, where preliminary results suggest a broad-spectrum anticancer effect ⁵⁵. Several clinical trials are currently underway to further assess its safety and synergistic potential in combination regimens, particularly in breast and prostate cancer populations ^{54,56}. Although the current findings are encouraging, challenges remain in defining the optimal dosing strategies, treatment combinations, and patient populations most likely to benefit. Nevertheless, disulfiram exemplifies the potential of drug repurposing as a strategic approach to expanding therapeutic options in oncology.

3.9 Mebendazole:

Mebendazole, a benzimidazole compound traditionally used as an anti-helminthic agent, has recently gained attention for its potential application in oncology. Initially approved for treating parasitic infections, its repurposing as an anticancer drug was found by

preclinical studies revealing potent antitumor activity across a variety of malignancies, including osteosarcoma, melanoma, and glioblastoma ⁵⁸. These findings were further supported by case reports in humans, suggesting clinically relevant anticancer effects and prompting further mechanistic investigation into its potential utility in oncology.

The anticancer mechanisms of mebendazole are diverse and extend beyond its known antiparasitic action. A primary mechanism involves the disruption of microtubule dynamics through inhibition of tubulin polymerization. This leads to mitotic arrest and apoptotic cell death in tumor cells ⁵⁹. Additionally, mebendazole has been found to inhibit angiogenesis by interfering with vascular development, a critical process in tumor progression (Popović et al., 2017). It also induces apoptosis through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and mitochondrial dysfunction, particularly in melanoma models ⁶⁰. Notably, mebendazole has shown synergistic potential when combined with radiation or chemotherapeutic agents, improving overall survival in preclinical settings, such as in models of meningioma ⁶¹.

Experimental and clinical research has examined its efficacy across a range of cancers. In melanoma, mebendazole has demonstrated significant cytotoxic effects and apoptotic activity ⁶⁰. In meningioma, its combination with radiotherapy has led to improved survival outcomes in animal models ⁶¹. Additional studies have reported its activity against lung, colorectal, breast, and ovarian cancers, highlighting its broad-spectrum anticancer potential (Popović et al., 2017). Several clinical trials are currently underway to evaluate the safety and therapeutic efficacy of mebendazole in cancer patients, with early findings supporting its potential viability as a repurposed agent ⁵⁹. Comprehensive randomized clinical trials remain essential to validate mebendazole's role in oncology. Further research will be critical to optimize its use in combination regimens and define its therapeutic scope across different tumor types.

3.10 Itraconazole:

Itraconazole (ITZ), an antifungal agent commonly used to treat systemic mycoses, has gained considerable attention as a repurposed drug in oncology. Its anticancer properties were identified through drug repurposing screens, which revealed its ability to inhibit key cellular pathways involved in tumor growth and resistance. These findings have been validated by several preclinical studies and early-phase clinical trials, marking ITZ as a promising candidate in the development of low-cost, broad-spectrum cancer therapeutics.

One of the primary mechanisms by which itraconazole exerts anticancer effects is through inhibition of the Hedgehog (Hh) signaling pathway. It blocks the activity of smoothened receptors (SMO), thereby preventing downstream activation of glioma-associated

oncogene homologs (GLI1 and GLI2), which are often overexpressed in cancerous tissues^{62,63}. In addition to its role in suppressing signalling, ITZ interferes with tumour angiogenesis by disrupting the formation of new blood vessels and reversing chemoresistance mediated by efflux transporters such as P-glycoprotein⁶⁴. Moreover, the drug induces G1-phase cell cycle arrest and promotes apoptosis in various malignancies, including oesophageal cancer, where it suppresses the HER2/AKT signalling axis⁶⁵.

Therapeutically, ITZ has demonstrated efficacy as a monotherapy in prostate cancer and basal cell carcinoma, with favourable outcomes reported in clinical settings⁶⁴. Its antitumor activity has also been explored in oesophageal cancer, where ongoing trials are assessing its ability to downregulate HER2 expression and suppress tumour progression⁶⁵. Additionally, combination regimens involving ITZ have shown promise in treating relapsed non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), ovarian cancer, and triple-negative breast cancer, where it appears to enhance the efficacy of standard chemotherapeutic agents^{63,64}.

Clinical development of ITZ in oncology continues, with ongoing studies such as the Phase I trial (NCT02749513) investigating its impact on HER2 modulation in oesophageal carcinoma patients⁶⁵. Previous trials have also supported its role in improving response rates to chemotherapy, underscoring its therapeutic versatility. Despite encouraging results, challenges such as drug resistance and variability in response require further investigation to optimize its clinical use. Nonetheless, itraconazole remains a compelling example of how repositioned drugs can provide new avenues for cancer treatment at reduced developmental costs.

4. Clinical Trial Design and Regulatory Landscape for Repurposed Drugs:

Repurposing existing drugs for cancer treatment offers cost-effective alternative to traditional drug development, but it faces significant clinical and regulatory challenges. Even though the safety profiles of these drugs are well known they still require cancer specific clinical trials to demonstrate efficacy. Preclinical phases can often be shortened, unlike new cancer drugs that need large phase III trials, repurposed drugs may be validated through smaller, targeted studies especially if they show strong benefits in specific patient groups. However, bringing them into clinical use is often difficult due to lack of commercial incentive, especially for generic or off-patent drugs. These drugs often termed as financial orphans receive little support for regulatory approval or marketing. They are usually tested in combination with standard therapies requiring careful trial design⁶⁶. Most clinical trials are funded by pharmaceutical companies which usually have little interest in supporting trials for repurposed drugs especially when those drugs are generics are close to patent expiry. Without the

promise of financial return, these companies rarely invest in large scale studies leaving a gap in evidence needed to integrate such drugs into primary oncology care. Some researchers also suggest that smaller phase II or pivotal trials if well conducted should be accepted for regulatory approval and clinical decision making in repurposing contexts. Regulatory innovations like U.S FDAs breakthrough therapy designations are highlighted as promising steps through similar frameworks are still lacking in many other regions like European Union. When aiming for on-label approval formal regulatory pathways such as type II variations or well-established use applications require substantial clinical evidence and come with high costs, often exceeding 2,90,000 euros in EMA. Most repurposing trails especially in late stages are led by academic or non-commercial sponsors who often lack regulatory expertise and funding needed to turn promising results into approved indications. While over 280 candidates are in repurposing pipeline as per reDO database only a fraction reach phase II/III trials. Initiatives like EUs STAMP framework which supports collaborations between academic researchers and industry through regulatory guidance and pilot programs along with giving incentives like fee waivers and clearer regulatory pathways that help bring effective low-cost cancer treatments to patients faster⁶⁷. While the genomic revolution has brought remarkable insights us has largely focused on single gene targets and often overlooked broader principles of cancer biology and pharmacology. Repurposed drugs gave a key advantage of already available safety, dosing and interaction profiles reducing the need for early-stage trials and regulatory complications. From patients' perspective this means more accessible treatment options including combinations that might be better tolerated. For clinicians it gives opportunity to choose drugs that are not under conventional therapies that are too toxic and ineffectively include using pharmacokinetics to set starting doses, running hospital-based trials with real world patients and tailoring doses based on pharmacogenomics and using therapeutic drug monitoring to optimise treatment over time⁶⁸.

Overall, the success of repurposed cancer drugs depends not only on well-designed clinical trials but also on accessible regulatory pathways, financial incentives and collaborative models that can bridge gap between academic innovation and formal approval.

5. Challenges in Cancer drug repurposing:

Despite its promise, cancer drug repurposing comes with a unique set of challenges One such major issue is biological complexity and variability of tumours, many studies overlook the underlying molecular signatures that determine treatment effectiveness. Clinical trials in this space often have a small sample sizes run for short periods, or use inconsistent dosing strategies, all of

which reduce their reliability and statistical strength. Another concern is that important factors like patient ethnicity are frequently ignored, even though they can significantly affect how drugs work and how safe they are. On the regulatory side researchers must navigate evolving guidelines meet demands for subgroup analyses and often work with drugs that may not reach effective tissue concentrations at standard doses ⁶⁹. Pharmaceutical companies often lack funding and may prioritize popular easy to access drugs over those with real potential. Clinically cancers complexity especially in combination therapies make trials more expensive and very hard to design. Recruiting patients is another challenge, and comorbidities in cancer patients can increase the risk of unexpected side effects. When it comes to computational predictions that are good as the data and lab-based screening methods are often too costly and for non-commercial institutions. These multi-factorial challenges, from financial disincentives and trial design limitations to biological complexity and regulatory constraints and help in innovative strategies to realize the full potential of drug repurposing in oncology.

Future directions: Harnessing integrated multi-omics platforms and AI-driven models to better identify and prioritize candidate drugs tailored to patient-specific molecular profiles. Expanding use of

patient-derived organoids and 3D cultures can enhance preclinical validation, while adaptive clinical trial designs like basket and umbrella trials offer efficient pathways to test repurposed agents in biomarker-stratified populations. Collectively, these strategies can accelerate bench to bedside transition of repurposed drugs, making precision therapies more accessible and cost cost-effective.

6. CONCLUSION:

Drug repurposing holds transformative potential in oncology by offering faster, safer, and more cost-effective options, especially valuable in an era where conventional drug development struggles to keep pace with patient needs. Despite clear scientific promise, there are hurdles, and underpowered clinical trials continue to progress slowly. Bridging these gaps will require innovative patient-centred trial designs, smarter use of real data, and collaborative models that prioritize public health over patents. With continued investment and global cooperation, drug repurposing can become a foundation of precision oncology and a lifeline for patients awaiting better care.

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Drug Name	Original Indication	Cancer Application(s)	Mechanism(s) of Action	Clinical Trials	Status/Notes
Metformin	Type 2 diabetes	Breast, colorectal, endometrial, pancreatic, prostate, lung	AMPK activation, mTOR inhibition, insulin/IGF suppression, immune modulation	NCT01101438 (breast) NCT01210911 (pancreatic)	Multiple phase II/III trials
Aspirin	Pain/inflammation, CVD prevention	Colorectal, breast, prostate, gastric, ovarian	COX-2 inhibition, platelet inactivation, NF-κB suppression, Wnt/β-catenin block	NCT02301286 (prevention) NCT00565708 (colorectal)	Prevention and adjuvant trials
Propranolol	Hypertension, arrhythmia, anxiety	Angiosarcoma, melanoma, breast, HCC	β ₂ -adrenergic blockade, anti-angiogenesis (VEGF), anti-migration,	NCT01847001 (breast) NCT05037993 (melanoma) NCT04357841 (angiosarcoma)	Multiple phase II/III trials

			apoptosis; stress signalling inhibition		
Carvedilol	Heart failure, hypertension	Lung, breast, HCC, head & neck	β/α - blockade, ROS induction, EGFR/MAP K inhibition, apoptosis, reversal of resistance	NCT05096120 (breast)	Phase II ongoing
Atorvastatin	Hypercholesterol emia	Breast, prostate, colorectal, liver, kidney, lung	Inhibits HMG-CoA reductase, ↓ prenylation (RAS), pro- apoptotic, anti- angiogenesis	NCT03854799 (ovarian) NCT04170987 (colorect al)	Phase II/III trials
Simvastatin	Hypercholesterol emia	Glioblastom a, liver, Breast, colorectal, prostate, lung, gastric	Similar to atorvastatin; also induces cell-cycle arrest, ↓ MMP-2/NF- κ B	NCT03370431 (glioblast oma) NCT04261855 (liver)	Phase II ongoing
Thalidomide & IMiDs (lenalidomide, pomalidomide)	Sedative, then MM/MDS	Multiple myeloma, lymphoma, MDS, prostate, HCC, renal, ovarian	Cereblon E3 ligase modulation → IKZF1/3 degradation, anti- angiogenesis , immune activation	NCT00033332 (thalidom ide) NCT00480363 (lenalido mide)	FDA- approved, ongoing trials
Chloroquine / Hydroxychloro quine	Malaria, autoimmune	NSCLC, melanoma, myeloma, breast, Pancreatic, glioblastom a, combo trials	Autophagy inhibition, TLR9/p53 modulation, immune enhancement	NCT01978184 (pancreat ic) NCT02378532 (glioblast oma)	Combo studies, >30 trials
Disulfiram	Alcohol dependence	Glioblastom a, breast, prostate	Copper- mediated ROS, proteasome/ NF- κ B inhibition, ALDH inhibition, CSC	NCT02678975 (glioblast oma)	Phase I/II

			targeting		
Mebendazole	Anthelmintic	Glioblastoma, colorectal	Microtubule disruption, VEGF/MMP suppression, CSC/ABL1 targeting, apoptosis induction	NCT02644291 (glioblastoma)	Phase I/II
Itraconazole	Antifungal	Prostate, basal cell, lung	Hedgehog inhibition, anti-angiogenesis, mTOR block, P-gp reversal, immune effects	NCT01787331 (prostate)	Phase II ongoing

Table 1: Repurposed Drugs for Cancer Treatment

Note: ALDH – aldehyde dehydrogenase; AMPK – AMP-activated protein kinase; COX – cyclo-oxygenase; HMG-CoA – 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-glutaryl-coenzyme A; IGF – insulin-like growth factor; IMiDs – immunomodulatory imide drugs; mTOR – mechanistic target of rapamycin; ROS – reactive oxygen species

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